

OPERAS-D

DESIGN FOR OPEN ACCESS PUBLICATIONS IN EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREAS FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

WP 5 – Dissemination, communication and exploitation

D5.3 Exploitation guide v.1 (first draft)

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DRAFT VERSION

DESIGN FOR OPEN ACCESS PUBLICATIONS IN EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREAS FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

Deliverable 5.3

Exploitation guide

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Abstract

Introduction

The OPERAS-D (Design) project supports the 9 main partners (“core group”) of the OPERAS network in the development of a European e-infrastructure for open access publications in the SSH. The project addresses long-term requirements for the development of the e-infrastructure and community building, as well as seeks to expand other interested parties within and beyond Europe, and in diverse fields of the SSH. To achieve this goal, the key objectives of the OPERAS-D project are to prepare a design study that defines governance models, structures and scientific and technical concepts for future services that the infrastructure will provide and establishes a roadmap to achieve these goals according to the requirements for long term sustainability. OPERAS-D engages the current and future partners in the OPERAS network to strengthen the community and develop the network of partners participating in OPERAS across Europe, specifically in central European countries.

Task 5.5, Exploitation Strategy, outlines the exploitation strategy of OPERAS and describes how the consortium and project partners will seek to exploit the results of the project. This Deliverable 5.3, Exploitation guide, is the result of Task 5.5. The current version is the first draft of D5.3, to be finalized by April 30. The task is part of WP 5 – Dissemination, communication and exploitation (M1-18), which deals with awareness, outreach, in-reach, engagement and collective exploitation actions to maximise the impact of the project during the project and afterwards.

Exploitation strategy

The aim of the exploitation strategy is to outline how the results of the OPERAS-D project will be used. As OPERAS-D is a project to prepare all future activities of OPERAS, the exploitation of the project results is an integral part of the project.

The exploitation strategy is based on three tracks:

1. **Consolidating results of project in the Design Study**
 - Update Design Study
 - Disseminate Design Study

1. **Developing roadmaps for future development**
 - Future development of e-infrastructure governance and business model

- Design and roadmap of future services
- Network building

1. **Engaging partners in core activities**

- Establishing Working Groups
- Producing white papers on key topics
- Implementing recommendations

Exploitation guide

This Exploitation guide looks at the three main tracks described in the Exploitation strategy and at how OPERAS partners will continue to operate after the close of OPERAS-D. The guide addresses two scenarios, depending on the outcome on the OPERAS application to become part of the ESFRI roadmap: the first scenario presumes OPERAS will be accepted on the roadmap, the second scenario presumes OPERAS will be rejected. In each case, this guide follows the three tracks and presents a short roadmap on how OPERAS will continue in each of these areas of activity.

The three tracks of the Exploitation strategy

Consolidating results of project in Design study

The Design study describes the core elements for the future development of OPERAS as a distributed e-infrastructure for open scholarly communication.

All project results are collected and integrated in the Design study, which consists of the following central elements: landscape study, usage survey, and business and governance model. The Design study will be updated towards the end of the project (D2.4) to encompass most of the OPERAS-D deliverables:

- Landscape study
- OPERAS Technical map
- Survey on optimizing e-infrastructure investments
- Design and roadmap for Future services
- OPERAS business and Governance plan
- Legal study and documentation
- Roadmap for developing e-infrastructure
- Network building

Other results include the Public website and toolbox (D5.2) and the Communication and dissemination guide (D5.1).

Developing roadmaps for future development

The roadmaps are a specific part of the OPERAS-D project, set up to plan the central activities within OPERAS:

- Future development of e-infrastructure (D2.4)
- Future development of services (D3.3)
- Network building (D2.2)

Network building is an ongoing activity within OPERAS-D, building on the identification of key stakeholders involved in e-infrastructures through the landscape study and exploring avenues for community building, making use of various instruments, such as validation workshops and other events, and an online survey.

Engaging partners in core activities through Working Groups

This part of the Exploitation strategy is also an ongoing OPERAS activity, not limited to the OPERAS-D project period. The goal of this activity is first of all to engage all partners in the development of OPERAS. The OPERAS core group has established a range of Working Groups to address all future activities. These Working Groups consist of representatives of all OPERAS partners. All partners are obliged to take part in one or more Working Groups.

The Working Groups, coordinated by members of the Core group of OPERAS, are organised around the following topics:

- Communication
- Tools (R&D)
- Standards
- Business models
- Best practices
- Multilingualism
- Platforms and Services

Preparing future activities and projects through white papers

The Working Groups do research on their topic, build expertise, and help prepare for future projects. Within the OPERAS-D project, the Working Groups are required to produce a white paper on their topic. These white papers build on the Design study and are meant as a preparation for future activities and projects.

In particular, the white papers provide input for OPERAS partners to collaborate in various ways: to share services, adopt standards, implement best practises, and integrate within EOSC. This happens at three levels:

1. Upgrade existing publishing services, through:
 - Communication and advocacy for Open Science;
 - Training for publishers and researchers;
 - Research & Development to provide innovative tools;
 - Development of sustainable and fair business models for open access.
1. Integrate to the European Open Science Cloud, through:
 - Standardization of technologies and information systems;
 - Adoption of scientific and editorial best practices;
 - Interoperability with other infrastructures at different levels.
1. Offer unified services in the European Research Area:
 - OPERAS Certification Service (DOAB);
 - OPERAS Discovery Service (Isidore);
 - OPERAS Research for Society Service (Hypotheses).

Scenario 1: OPERAS on ESFRI Roadmap

This is the main scenario for OPERAS. We expect to know the outcome in June 2018. The OPERAS Design study is based on this scenario, which means we can follow the three tracks as described in the Exploitation strategy. In particular, we can work according to the Roadmaps for future development (track 2) and continue work within the Working groups (track 3).

The first goal will be to prepare for the next INFRADEV call, due in November 2018, with a deadline for submission of proposals in March 2019. Preparation for this call can start after the close of OPERAS-D in June. It should be noted that there won't be any specific funding available for OPERAS activities until around mid-July 2019 (outside the ongoing projects, in particular HIRMEOS, and French funding through PIA, for the central office).

Next steps in this scenario

In the period leading up to the call in November, we can prepare along the following lines of activities:

1. Coordinate with the European Commission to prepare for future calls (this is only possible before calls are issued);
2. Finalization of White papers within the Working groups;
3. Dissemination of White papers
4. Prepare project proposal for INFRADEV call;
5. Prepare project proposal for the second central platform, the Discovery service for INFRAEOSC call.
6. Prepare project proposal for the third central platform, the Research for Society service for SWAFS call.
7. Consolidation of OPERAS governance
8. Further networking with other infrastructures
9. Integrating White papers in 'living' book publication 'State of the art in HSS', connected to updated resource with the different results from the Working Groups.

Ad.2 and 3) The first drafts of the White papers will be presented during the final OPERAS-D conference in Athens (May 30-June 1). The White papers will be finalized following the conference and then disseminated.

Ad.4) The project proposal for the INFRADEV call (INFRADEV-02-2019, due to be issued in October, with deadline for submission in January 2019) can be prepared by developing various workpackages, that can be extracted from the White papers. This will involve making an inventory of future services and establishing a procedure to select and prioritize these services. The work will be coordinated by the Core group, in collaboration with members from the Working groups.

Ad.5) The project proposal for the INFRAEOSC call, the Discovery service, is already being prepared through a specific project, DISPOSED-H, funded by ANR and coordinated by Huma-Num. Preparation regards the call INFRAEOSC-02-2019, due to be issued in November 2018, and involves a number of meetings and workshops until November, with preliminary project partners.

Ad.6) The project proposal for the SWAFS call, the Research for Society service, is being prepared through a specific activity coordinated by OpenEdition. Preparation regards the call SWAFS-15-2018-2019 due to be issued in December 2018. A funding support will be sought for from ANR before June 2018.

Ad.7) The consolidation of OPERAS governance scheme will be conducted during the second semester of 2018 with the establishment of applications rules and procedures for new potential partners and the routinization of Core Groups activity to strengthen the decision-making process.

Ad.8) Based on the first contacts established during the preparation of the Design study and the existing list of “liaison officers” in OPERAS, the bilateral and multilateral relations with other infrastructures will have to be reinforced. Bilateral: Dariah, OpenAire, ENRESSH. Multilateral: RI-Train, ERIC-Forum, SSH cluster of ERICs.

Ad.9) The plan is to integrate the results of all of the White papers in a book publication, which should be published by one of our partners. The publication will be connected to a resource with all the specific data from the White papers, which can be kept up-to-date, hence a ‘living’ book. The deadline for publication should ideally be January 2019, ahead of the submission of the first project proposals.

Further activity planning for scenario 1

Further activity planning will be based on the Updated Design study, integrating the results of the OPERAS-D project. The final Exploitation guide will make use of these results, but the main components of the work ahead are provided in the available Design Study, notably the Work Breakdown Structure which is part of the Governance and Business model (table 5 and figure 1, page 39 and 40).

Scenario 2: OPERAS not on ESFRI Roadmap

In the event that OPERAS is not accepted on the ESFRI roadmap, the Design study will need to be adapted (track 1), especially the Governance and Business model. This will also involve the Roadmaps for future development (track 2). The third track, regarding the Working groups, might be less influenced by this scenario, provided OPERAS maintains its momentum and relevance.

Scenario 2 implies that OPERAS will not be able to apply for INFRADEV calls, that are designed to support the development future ESFRI’s. INFRADEV funding was meant to support a central part of the future development of OPERAS: the implementation of the governance model and legal framework; the Shared services (Toolbox; Best practices; Business models: Journal flipping model; Library based model; Services market place).

However, OPERAS will still have access to funding for the development of the central platforms. In addition, part of the development work is already being done within HIRMEOS: this includes tools and services for OA books (Identifiers, Entity recognition, Annotation, Metrics service), EOSC integration for OA books, and the development of one of the Central platforms: the certification service provided by DOAB.

Next steps in this scenario

1. Review and revision of Design study and Roadmaps;
2. Finalization of White papers within the Working groups;
3. Prepare project proposal for the second central platform, the Discovery service for INFRAEOSC;
4. Finalisation of the HIRMEOS project;
5. Explore pilot project for third Central platform, the Research for Society service, for SWAFS;
6. Follow up of Working groups, explore the development of future services and tools, where possible.
7. Integrating White papers in a 'living' book publication 'State of the art in HSS', connected to updated resource with all the specific results from the Working Groups.

Ad.1) Review and revision of the Design study and Roadmaps will be a central effort to be undertaken by the Core group. This should direct the activities of OPERAS in the next 3 to 5 years. It should include a new approach to the consortium as a whole. We return to this effort in the following paragraph.

Ad.2 and 3) This work remains the same as in scenario 1.

Ad.4) The HIRMEOS project will continue until June 2019. The project will result in the technical implementation of various services across participating platforms, but there remains considerable potential to work with new partners and develop use cases for specific applications based on the HIRMEOS services, including the potential for central services such as the Metrics service and the OA Market place.

Ad.5) The project proposal for the SWAFS call, the Research for Society service, is being prepared through a specific activity coordinated by OpenEdition. Preparation regards the call SWAFS-15-2018-2019 due to be issued in December 2018. A funding support will be sought for from ANR before June 2018.

Ad.6) This work starts with extracting an inventory of potential services and tools from the White papers as in scenario 1, but it will also involve finding a new approach to develop and share these services, including new funding options and supporting the OPERAS network in different ways. The work will be coordinated by the Core group, in collaboration with members from the Working groups.

Ad.7) This work remains the same as in scenario 1, but it serves as an added incentive for the Working groups to continue their work in scenario 2.

OPERAS Design study for scenario 2

A central conclusion in scenario 2 could be that OPERAS will not develop into a Research Infrastructure as planned, and that it must develop a new model for the future. The model for OPERAS could be to develop into an e-infrastructure. As such OPERAS could aim to strengthen its capacity by developing a strategic partnership with one or more related infrastructures. Potential candidates for such partnerships are DARIAH (a RI), OpenAIRE (e-infrastructure), and SCOSS (community infrastructure providing a sustainability model). Each of these potential partnerships would impact on the focus and scope of OPERAS:

- Dariah: would lead OPERAS to a strongly disciplinary focused pathway, to provide support services to humanities research exclusively.
- OpenAire: would lead OPERAS to widen its scope beyond SSH and focus more on IT services, becoming more technical.
- SCOSS: it would lead to a transformation of OPERAS into a loose network identifying services to be funded through SCOSS. Considering the scope of SCOSS, it would mean that OPERAS would lose its European focus. OPERAS network wouldn't have to make efforts to align on the EC strategy but rather on SCOSS funders' strategy, with stronger representation from the US.

Whatever the outcome, the revised Design study should result in a new Governance and Business model, a new legal framework, new roadmaps for future services and a new plan for Network building, including the potential for partnerships. It would be preferable if this study could be done in a relatively short time frame, as there is ongoing work in other areas (Working groups, preparing project proposals).

